

testingCheckerFinderSalamander uses a series of images of a checkerboard in the testing arena and the MATLAB function, `detectCheckerboardPoints` to calibrate pairs of cameras.

salamanderGlidingGenerateWorldPoints generates a three-dimensional reconstruction of the salamanders' paths through the testing arena. It uses the information from the tracked landmarks in the `xypts` file generated using DLT and the camera calibration information generated by `testingCheckerFinderSalamander` to do this. It then uses two reference vectors to rotate the reconstruction to match its reference axes to our world axes. The x-axis is constrained using the bottom of the side wall and the z-axis is constrained using gravity as shown by a falling ball.

salamanderDataSmoothingFinal applies a quintic spline smoothing algorithm to the three-dimensional data generated in `salamanderGlidingGenerateWorldPoints`. It interpolates position data for frame in which points on the salamander were obstructed. It also calculates instantaneous velocity and acceleration using the first- and second-derivatives of the spline function respectively.

salamanderGlidingVariableFinal calculates the performance and biomechanical variables that we were interested in measuring.

Smoothing Tolerances.xlsx contains all of the custom smoothing tolerances found to be ideal for every single trial. We painstakingly adjusted smoothing tolerance in every video analyzed and this spreadsheet lists the ultimate tolerances used for every individual trial.

WindTunnel_Means_and_Variation.xlsx includes all recorded measurements of wind speed with a digital anemometer and describes exactly how wind speed was measured and with what kind of replication.